

Sample Name: PET UV 1 μm

Material: Polyethylene terephthalate

Size: <1 μm

Production Partner: TNO

Storage Conditions: Refrigerated

Summary

Physical Characteristics

- Median diameter (D_{50_v}) = 0,88 μm
- Particles have an irregular morphology
- $3,5 \times 10^{11}$ particles per gram
- 20739 cm^2/g surface area

Chemical Characteristics

- >99% $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{O}_4$ (PET) determined by XRF
- No changes due to milling or aging observed in FTIR spectrum
- Not able to obtain a cathodoluminescence spectrum

Description of terms

- $D[4,3]$: Volume mean (μm)
- $D[3,2]$: Surface area mean (μm)
- $D[2,1]$: Spherical particle mean (μm)
- $D[1,0]$: Number length mean (μm)
- D_{50_v} : Median diameter (volume basis, μm)
- D_{50_N} : Median diameter (number basis, μm)
- N_w : Number of particles per gram plastic (#/g)
- A_w : Surface area of particles per gram plastic (cm^2/g)

Particle Size Distribution (using Static Light Scattering (SLS) provided by TNO)

D[4,3]	D[3,2]	D[2,1]	D[1,0]	D50 _N	D50 _V	N _w	A _w
4,08	2,54	1,64	1,15	0,88	3,04	$3,5 \times 10^{11}$	20739

Chemical Composition (using XRF provided by Malvern Panalytical)

Chemical formula	Concentration (%)
$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{O}_4$	99,93
Element	Concentration (ppm)
Si	134
S	12
Cl	335
K	14
Ca	4
Ti	1
Cr	19
Fe	76
Ni	10
Cu	6
Zn	2
Mo	1
Pb	1

Chemical Bonding (Using μ -FTIR provided by TNO)Cathodoluminescence Spectroscopy (provided by TNO)

Not available